

Global Buildings Database Seed on Whole Life Carbon Emissions, Energy Performance, and Material Intensity (GBDB CarbEnMats)

Authors

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Abstract

Globally, interest in understanding the whole life cycle related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of buildings is increasing. Robust data is required for benchmarking and analysis of parameters driving so-called 'whole life carbon' (WLC) emissions, but also the energy and material flows.

Here the seed for a global buildings database (GBDB) on whole life carbon, energy performance, and material intensity of buildings is presented. GBDB compiles information on more than 1,200 building case studies and includes 155 attributes in its core version and more than 330 attributes overall. It provides insights on context and site, building design, assessment methods, energy performance and material intensity, as well as GHG emissions across the different building life cycle stages. GBDB contains more than 130,000 specified building data points, representing more than 5,000,000 square meters of floor space. The data was collected through various meta-studies, combining both data from scientific literature as well as industry sources, using dedicated data collection templates and Python scripts for data processing, all of which are available alongside this descriptor.

Background & Summary

The need for radically reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions globally demands defining and implementing thorough assessments and performance classes for both operational and embodied GHG emissions of buildings to provide relevant guidance for policymakers and practitioners^{1,2}. The topic of so-called whole life carbon (WLC) of buildings is gaining increasing attention among decision-makers concerned with climate and industrial policy, as well as building procurement, design, and operation^{3,4}. However, most open buildings datasets published thus far have been focusing on building's operational energy consumption and related parameters⁵⁻⁸. Recent years furthermore brought large-scale datasets on building geometry (footprint, height)^{9,10} as well as the publication of some datasets on building construction systems and material intensity¹¹⁻¹⁵. Heeren and Fishman's database seed on material intensity (MI) of buildings¹³, an essential inspiration for this work, was a first step towards an open data repository on material-related environmental impacts of buildings. In their 2019 descriptor, the authors present data on the material coefficients of more than 300 building cases intended for use in studies applying material flow analysis (MFA), input-output (IO) or life cycle assessment (LCA) methods. Furthermore, Yang et al.¹⁵ established an MI database for Chinese urban buildings with 813 samples. Sprecher et al.¹⁴ presented MI data for

46 Dutch buildings, compiling data on 61 large scale demolition projects. Guven et al.¹² elaborated
47 on these efforts by publishing a construction classification system database for understanding
48 resource use in building construction. And most recently, Fishman et al.¹¹ published RASMI,
49 which provides global ranges of building material intensities differentiated by region, structure,
50 and function. However, there is still a lack of publicly available data that combines material
51 intensity, energy performance as well as assesses life cycle-related environmental impacts,
52 such as life cycle-related GHG emissions, i.e. building's whole life carbon.

53 Here we present a global buildings database seed on whole life carbon emissions, energy
54 performance, and material intensity (GBDB CarbEnMats). This GBDB dataset provides
55 information on more than 1,200 buildings worldwide, representing more than 5,000,000
56 square meters of floor space. The database contains more than 130,000 specified building data
57 points. The dataset includes attributes on geographical context and site, main building design
58 characteristics, LCA-based assessment methods, as well as information on energy and material
59 use, and related WLC emissions with a focus on embodied carbon (EC) emissions. The dataset
60 compiles data obtained through a systematic review of the scientific literature as well as
61 systematic data collection from both literature sources and industry partners. By applying a
62 uniform data collection template (DCT) and related automated procedures for systematic data
63 collection and compilation, we facilitate the processing, analysis and visualization along
64 predefined categories and attributes, and support the consistency of data types and units. The
65 descriptor includes specifications related to the DCT spreadsheet form used for obtaining these
66 data as well as explanations of the data processing and feature engineering steps undertaken
67 to clean and harmonise the data records. The validation focuses on describing the composition
68 of the dataset and values observed for attributes related to whole life carbon, energy
69 performance and material intensity. The data published with this descriptor offers the largest
70 open compilation of data on whole life cycle emissions, energy performance and material
71 intensity of buildings published to date.

72 This open dataset is expected to be valuable for research applications in the context of
73 approaches like material flow analyses (MFA), input-output analyses (I/O) and building LCA
74 modelling. It offers a unique data source for benchmarking whole life carbon in context of
75 buildings' energy performance and material intensity to inform policy and decision-making
76 decarbonization of building construction and operation as well as for informing sustainable real
77 estate practices. The data are particularly suitable for gaining insights on the scale and
78 proportions of the corresponding values to be able to carry out benchmarking and plausibility
79 checks in future studies. At the same time, the analysis of the case study sources used provides
80 insights into the status of the type, scope, level of detail and completeness of the description of
81 the objects of assessment reported. This reveals considerable gaps that can lead to
82 uncertainties in the evaluation. This article includes suggestions for an extensive list of
83 attributes that should be used for the description of building case studies. It is also intended as
84 a call to improve transparency and traceability in the documentation of building LCA studies in
85 both research and industry practice. This database seed is intended as a starting point for
86 further and more comprehensive publications on whole life carbon building data in the future.

87 **Methods**

88 ***Data collection***

89 **Phases**

90 This GBDB has been established through systematic reviews of suitable data from the scientific
91 literature as well as through data collection from industry partners. The dataset strongly builds
92 on data obtained via the systematic review and meta-study of the published scientific
93 literature¹ as part of the International Energy Agency (IEA) Energy in Buildings and Communities

94 (EBC) Technology Collaboration Programme (TCP) research project “Annex 72 - Assessing Life
 95 Cycle Related Environmental Impacts Caused by Buildings”¹⁶, as well as the screening and data
 96 acquisition from industry partners within the project “Towards Embodied Carbon Benchmarks
 97 for Buildings across Europe”^{17,18}.

98 *Table 1: Four main phases and related key sources for establishing this dataset.*

Phase	Period	Description
1	2018-2019	The foundation of this database was established within the systematic review, data collection and meta-analysis of scientific literature on embodied versus operational carbon of buildings conducted by experts of IEA EBC Annex 72 and presented in related publications ^{1,19} .
2	2019-2020	Consecutive elaboration of the database by experts of IEA EBC Annex 72 with additional attributes (e.g., contextual attributes (such as seismic region), building geometry parameters, increased detail in results documentation (per life cycle stage)) as well as the inclusion of further case studies by adding the data from the primary sources ^{20,21} .
3	2020-2022	Extension of the database with more than 700 additional cases from countries across Europe within the Towards Embodied Carbon Benchmarks for Buildings across Europe (ECB) project, albeit with a limited set of attributes. Data provided/entered by the project team and external data partners. Details on the data curation, processing and engineering, and analysis have been presented in the related publications ^{18,22,23} .
4	2022-2024	Consolidation of the database with the engineering of additional secondary attributes, such as dedicated material intensity factors based on the primary information obtained in phases 1-3.

99 Sources

100 The database consists of 1294 datasets (i.e., rows) retrieved from four meta-analyses^{1,20,21,23}
 101 and the respective primary sources. *Table 2* outlines the number of cases (count) included from
 102 different meta-studies compiled in this database. We included all cases from those meta-
 103 studies where quantified results on whole life carbon emissions were available in the related
 104 articles in data tables, graphs, or relevant supplementary materials. The numbers in brackets
 105 indicate the total number of cases in the final sample of the respective meta-analyses, even
 106 those where eventually no data could be obtained from primary sources.

107 *Table 2: Overview of main data sources compiled in this dataset.*

Count	Description	Reference
331 (656)	Global dataset from SLR meta-analysis covering different residential and non-residential buildings, construction types found in scientific literature.	Röck et al. 2020 ¹
23 (50)	Dataset on wooden building case studies collected in Northern Hemisphere, different residential types and office buildings.	Amiri et al. 2020 ²⁰
86 (75)	Dataset on residential buildings in humid subtropical and tropical climates identified through SLR. Includes case study variants as individual cases.	Satola et al. 2021 ²¹
769 (769)	Europe-focused dataset from five EU countries compiled for benchmarking embodied carbon, various residential and non-residential building types.	Röck and Sørensen 2022 ²³
1294	Total cases in global buildings database seed (GBDB CarbEnMats)	

108 We note that the dataset established by Röck and Sørensen 2022²³, while publicly available
 109 and described in the related technical reports¹⁸ and conference paper²², has not yet been
 110 published in a scientific journal and thus has not previously undergone scientific peer-review.

111 Data processing

112 General remarks

113 A dedicated workflow was developed to prepare the raw primary data obtained through the
 114 data collection from academics, industry experts and national data partners. Building data was
 115 collected via a dedicated data collection template (DCT) spreadsheet (.xls/.gsheet) developed in
 116 several iterations for data collection within the aforementioned projects, starting from the
 117 definition of attributes found relevant from the experience of the involved experts and inspired
 118 by previous building LCA studies and meta-analyses^{24–30}. A dedicated workflow was developed
 119 to prepare the raw primary data obtained through the data collection from academics, industry

120 experts and national data partners. The workflow utilizes IPython in Jupyter Notebook ³¹ for
121 data processing, harmonization and feature engineering. In some cases, database entries have
122 been received in their native format instead of the developed DCT. In such cases the data was
123 pre-processed individually using tailormade scripts to transform (parse) the data and fit it to
124 the format of the DCT. The pre-processing steps include removing rows with invalid data,
125 translating and regrouping data into common formats and categories from the DCT and
126 collecting all data sources into one combined dataset. With the combined dataset, harmonised
127 values as well as new features (attributes) were computed to enable a broad range of analyses.

128 Harmonization steps

129 Embodied carbon (EC) values were harmonised to a common reference study period (RSP) of
130 50 years^{32,33}, a common choice in established building LCA practice. It is important to
131 understand that the intention of the RSP is not to mirror the actual building service life, but
132 rather to provide a common frame of reference when assessing and comparing different
133 buildings and options from an LCA perspective. EC values, if needed, were further scaled to a
134 value per m² gross floor area (GFA). For the data collected via the data collection template in
135 phase 3, emission values should be per m² GFA and year (kgCO₂eq/m²GFA/a) by default, based
136 on the RSP of the respective case. Hence, the harmonization of net floor area (NFA) to GFA is
137 not required. Harmonization of the RSPs is still implemented to improve comparability. For
138 data collected in phase 3, the approach for harmonizing EC values, builds on the disaggregated
139 emission data per life cycle stage. The life cycle stages are defined from the industry-wide
140 applied methods for life-cycle environmental performance of buildings presented in standards
141 ISO 21931-1:2022 and EN 15978:2011. Life cycle modules in stage A concern the production
142 and construction processes, modules in stage B concern the in-use processes, modules in stage
143 C concern the end-of-life (EoL) processes, and stage D concern the benefits and loads beyond
144 the system boundary. A comprehensive overview of the EN building life cycle stages is also
145 presented in the attributes Table 7.

146 The formulas applied for the harmonization of emission values to a common reference study
147 period (RSP) are:

148 (1) $GHG_{t(A,C),o} = GHG_{a(A,C),o} * RSP_o$

149 (2) $GHG_{t(B),h} = GHG_{a(B),o} * RSP_h$

150 where,

- 151 • GHG = GHG emission values
- 152 • RSP = Reference study period
- 153 • a = annualised
- 154 • h = harmonised
- 155 • o = original
- 156 • t = total

157 In the first step, the total of EC across the full life cycle of the respective case is computed.
158 Full life cycle EC values for life cycle stages A (production and construction processes) and C
159 (EoL processes) are computed using formula (1). These EC values are not scaled based on the
160 RSP for harmonisation (RSP_h), as the total emissions in A and C life cycle stages are not affected
161 by the RSP of a given study. Therefore, the original total value GHG_{t(A,C),o} can readily be used
162 in the database without further adaptations. On the other hand, total EC values from life cycle
163 modules in the use stage, i.e., stage B, are harmonised and scaled considering the factor
164 between the original RSP of the case study (RSP_o) and the RSP for harmonization (RSP_h) using
165 formula (2). This harmonization procedure enables scaling of use-stage related EC values and is
166 especially accurate for EC related to processes with a yearly frequency, such as cleaning and

167 maintenance activities (module B2). For repairs (B3) and replacement (B4), the results of the
 168 harmonization procedure can only offer an approximation, as the underlying processes usually
 169 have multi-annual frequency. While in line with respective building LCA standards at the time
 170 of writing, the change from original to harmonised RSP could, in practice, do affect the number
 171 of occurrences. Emission values for operational energy and water use (B6/B7) are scaled using
 172 the same logic applied as for the other use stage-related emissions. In the dataset, the different
 173 types of values are indicated via attribute extensions, where:

- 174 • `_m2` = Total GHG emissions across the full life cycle or respective life cycle stage
- 175 • `_m2a` = Annualised GHG emissions, based on respective RSP
- 176 • `_orig` = Values based on original RSP from source
- 177 • `_harm` = Values based on harmonised RSP, distinguishing life cycle stages¹⁸
- 178 • `_APEN` = Values harmonised for GFA and common RSP, unified life cycle¹

179 Material classification

180 The material quantities in this dataset were obtained through the selection of the “top 5”
 181 materials, i.e., the five most contributing materials in terms of total mass, based on their type
 182 and respective quantity. During data processing, this information was transformed to obtain
 183 the mass and material intensity of each of the materials available for selection and passed on to
 184 predefined options. Furthermore, the material mass and intensity were mapped with the
 185 Eurostat material categories for Material Flow Analysis (MFA) and environmental-economic
 186 accounts³⁴, to provide valuable information in the MFA context. A full list of the material
 187 classification and its subclasses is available in Annex A of the Economy-wide material flow
 188 accounts handbook. Table 3 shows the material options during primary input and related
 189 attribute (secondary), and mapping with Eurostat economy-wide material flow accounts³⁴ as
 190 well as¹³, listing the respective related attributes (secondary).

191 *Table 3: Material options for primary input and mapping with Eurostat material accounts, the H&F MI database*
 192 *seed, as well as the recent work of Fishman et al.*

Primary data collection		Secondary mappings		
Material options	Variable	Eurostat material accounts ³⁴	Heeren and Fishman ¹³	Fishman et al. ¹¹
Aluminium (e.g., alum alloy)	mass_aluminium	metal_materials	metals	aluminum
Bamboo	mass_bamboo	biomass_based_materials	bio-based	other
Brass, copper	mass_brass_copper	metal_materials	metals	copper
Cement mortar, plaster	mass_cement_mortar	non-metallic_minerals	CCA	concrete
Ceramics (e.g., fired clay bricks)	mass_ceramics	non-metallic_minerals	non-CCA-minerals	brick
Concrete reinforced	mass_concrete_reinforced	non-metallic_minerals	CCA	concrete
Concrete w/o reinforcement	mass_concrete_wo_reinforcement	non-metallic_minerals	CCA	concrete
Earth (unfired clay, adobe, rammed earth)	mass_earth	non-metallic_minerals	other-materials	other
EPS or XPS (insulation)	mass_EPS_XPS	fossil_energy_materials	other-materials	plastics
Fungi (e.g. Mycelium)	mass_fungi	biomass_based_materials	bio-based	other
Glass (single, double, triple)	mass_glass	non-metallic_minerals	non-CCA-minerals	glass
Metals (iron, steel)	mass_metals	metal_materials	metals	steel
Plastics (various: PC,	mass_plastics	fossil_energy_materials	other-materials	plastics

PE, PP, PU, PVC)				
Steel (reinforcement)	mass_steel_reinforcement	metal_materials	metals	steel
Stone (granite, limestone, etc)	mass_stone	non-metallic_minerals	non-CCA-minerals	other
Stone wool (e.g., insulation)	mass_stone_wool	non-metallic_minerals	non-CCA-minerals	other
Straw or hemp (e.g., strawbale)	mass_straw_hemp	biomass_based_materials	bio-based	other
Timber, wood	mass_wood	biomass_based_materials	bio-based	wood
Other	mass_other	-	-	other

193 Attribute priority

194 The complete attribute description (gbdb_attributes.XLSX) furthermore provides that attribute
 195 for prioritization. Prioritization of the attributes refers to the relevance of collecting data on a
 196 given attribute, in case data collection had to be reduced to a limited set of attributes due to
 197 time or resource constraints:

- 198 • A = Minimum information scope, most relevant attributes (high value, limited effort)
- 199 • B = Complete information scope, highly relevant attributes (high value, high effort)
- 200 • C = Extended information scope, nice to have (limited value, limited effort)
- 201 • D = Additional information, only if available (limited value, high effort)
- 202 • E = Administrative attributes and engineered data obtained through data processing

203 Furthermore, selected attributes are marked with indicators to note:

- 204 • * = Attributes included in phases 1 and 2, not phase 3 (as listed in Table 1).
- 205 • + = Attributes imputed if empty, either manually or automatically.

206 Datasets CORE and FULL

207 For improved usability we provide two versions of the dataset:

- 208 • a *CORE* set of attributes, which are defined by high priority and a generally, relatively
 209 high level of completeness in the present dataset. Particularly relevant attributes were
 210 included in the *CORE* set even if they show a low level of completeness, i.e., high level
 211 of missing values. The *CORE* dataset thus includes 155 attributes, mostly priority A/B,
 212 even if sparse, as well as C/D attributes, where reasonable completeness >50%.
- 213 • a *FULL* version of the dataset, which includes all 334 attributes and can be used for in-
 214 depth assessments using the additional information, including on the challenge of
 215 resolving prevailing data gaps in practice.

216 Data Records

217 Files

218 All files related to this database descriptor are available on a public GitHub repository
 219 (<https://github.com/mroeck/carbenmats-buildings>) and the related release via Zenodo
 220 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13221978>). The repository contains the following files:

- 221 • *README.MD* is a text file with instructions on how to use the files and documents.
- 222 • *gbdb_data_core.CSV* is the *CORE* building dataset in CSV text format (separator = ';').
- 223 • *gbdb_data_full.CSV* is the *FULL* building dataset in CSV text format (separator = ';').
- 224 • *gbdb_data.XLSX* is the building database in MS Excel format, containing both the *CORE*
 225 and *FULL* datasets in separate sheets, with *CORE* in the first sheet.
- 226 • *gbdb_attributes.XLSX* is a table with the complete attribute description.

- 227 • *gbdb_materials.XLSX* is a table for mapping the original material attributes with
228 different other common types of material classifications used in this database.
- 229 • *gbdb_py_benchmarking.IPYNB* is a Python Jupyter Notebook including code to define
230 data subsets for creating custom benchmark data tables for carbon and materials.
- 231 • *gbdb_py_visualizations.IPYNB* is a Python Jupyter Notebook for visualization of key
232 attributes and properties, some of which are presented in this descriptor.

233 **Types of attributes**

234 Overall, the global buildings database offers information on 1294 building cases around just
235 above 330 attributes (i.e., columns). *Figure 1* presents an overview of the attribute types and
236 some examples of attributes included in the dataset. A complete overview of the attributes is
237 provided in the data records ‘gbdb_attributes.XLS’.

238 To improve usability of the data, the most relevant and most complete 155 attributes are
239 compiled in the CORE dataset and presented in the following. These are distinguished into
240 attributes related to Metadata (see Table 4); Context and site (*Table 4*); Building design (*Table*
241 *5*); Assessment method (*Table 5*); Life cycle inventory (*Table 8*); Indicator results (*Table 10*).
242 The attributes in the complete overview files are further structured in subgroups, such as
243 General; Geometry; Energy; Materials; Carbon; Analytics.

244 The data is distinguished into two types of values based on their respective sources:

- 245 • Primary = Attributes requested to report in DCT, manual or automated input from the
246 original data source.
- 247 • Secondary = Attributes computed during processing, harmonization, and or feature
248 engineering.

249 All attributes (primary and secondary) are listed with respective descriptions and data type/unit
250 remarks, as well as prioritization (A-D) in the attribute description table (SI).

251 The attributes utilise three main data types:

- 252 • String/object: Usually given as ‘free text’. Also, the baseline type for unspecified data.
- 253 • Numerical: Numerical values, all implemented as floats (i.e., with possibility of decimal
254 values).
- 255 • Categorical: A *limited* set of values (i.e., categories) which can appear as both text and
256 numerical values.

257 The specific options for attributes listed as “categorical [predefined]”, or examples thereof, are
258 given in the spreadsheet ‘gbdb_attributes.XLS’, which is part of the data records provided.

259 **Attributes**

260 **Metadata**

261 *Table 4: CORE attributes for 'metadata'*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
meta_DOI_URL	DOI or reference (e.g., link) to the article/source	String (Free text)
meta_authors	Authors of the article/source	String (Free text)
meta_year	Year of publication/source	Numerical [integer]
meta_title	Title of publication/source	String (Free text)
meta_journal	Title of journal/publisher	String (Free text)

262 **Context and site**

263 *Table 4: CORE attributes for 'context and site'.*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
site_country	Country of construction	Categorical (Predefined)
site_country_iso	Country code acc. ISO 3166-1 ³⁵	Categorical (Predefined)
site_region_local	City or region (state, county) the case study building is located in.	String (Free text)
site_climate_zone	Climate zone acc. Koeppen-Geiger-Classification. ³⁶	Categorical (Predefined)
site_seismic_hazard	Seismic hazard level acc. global quake model. ³⁷	Categorical (Predefined)
site_region_geoscheme	World region based on United Nations geoscheme. ³⁵	Categorical (Predefined)

264 **Building design**

265 *Table 5: CORE attributes for 'building design'.*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
bldg_use_type	Building type	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_use_subtype	Building sub typology	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_project_type	Project type/concept with implications on scope of the assessment, i.e., new construction, a refurbishment case, comparative study, etc.	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_project_status	Project type	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_year_complete	Year of construction completion	Numerical [integer]
bldg_year_complete_interval	Year of construction completion interval	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_users_total	Number of users [n] (Residential= Occupants or beds; Office = desks or fulltime employees (FTE); Schools = Pupils; Hospital = Beds)	Numerical [decimal]
bldg_area_per_user	Floor area per user	Numerical [m2/cap]
bldg_area_definition	Gross Area Definition [m2]	String (Free text)
bldg_area_gfa	Gross Floor Area [m2]	Numerical [m2]
bldg_area_hfa	Heated Floor Area [m2]	Numerical [m2]
bldg_area_interval	Area interval (GFA) [m2]	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_floors_ag	Number of floors above ground [n]	Numerical [decimal]
bldg_floors_ag_interval	Number of floors above ground interval [n]	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_floors_bg	Number of floors below ground [n]	Numerical [decimal]
bldg_roof_type	Roof type in terms of geometry	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_area_value	Floor area of the building as per source. If possible, gross floor area (GFA).	Numerical [m2]
bldg_area_specification	Type of 'area', e.g., gross floor area (GFA), net floor area (NFA), or heated floor area (HFA), energy reference area (ERA), etc.	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_height	Building height (in meter), on highest point, i.e., ridge of the roof, if pitched roof.	Numerical [m]
bldg_footprint	Building footprint, i.e., the area covered by the building on the plot. Considered equivalent to projected roof area.	Numerical [m2]
bldg_energy_class_general	Energy Performance Class (Existing Standard = pre-2005 (prior to European Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EPBD)); New Standard = post-2005 (acc. EPBD); Advanced Standard = beyond regulatory minimum requirements, e.g., near/net zero energy buildings (NZEB), passive house)	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_energy_class_country	Energy performance class acc. to country definition	String (Free text)
bldg_QTO_type	Project data status	Categorical (Predefined)
bldg_struct_type	Structure type and main material	Categorical (Predefined)

266 **Assessment method**

267 *Table 5: CORE attributes for 'assessment methods': 'goal and scope' and 'life cycle impact assessment'.*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
lca_goal_scope	Goal of the study, as stated in source	String (Free text)
lca_reference_unit	Reference unit the results are primary expressed for, as stated in source (Not to be confused with functional unit, as here no performance criteria are specified)	String (Free text)
lca_functional_unit	Functional unit, i.e., functional equivalence specified for the assessment, as stated in the source.	String (Free text)
lca_RSP	Reference Study Period	Numerical [integer]
lca_software	LCA software	String (Free text)
lca_database	Primary environmental database / background data (& version)	String (Free text)
lca_database_version	Background data version (or I-O source)	String (Free text)
lca_database_other	Background data source - if 'other'	String (Free text)
lca_lcia_method	Impact assessment method (for GHG emissions, GWP indicator)	String (Free text)
lca_model_type	Type of LCA model	Categorical (Predefined)

268

269 **Building parts:** Specific attributes have been included in the dataset describing the scope of
 270 building parts covered in the respective case studies. The classification follows the building
 271 systems classification of the BB-CI/SfB construction indexing manual^{38,39}.

272 *Table 6: CORE attributes for 'assessment methods': 'building parts'*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
scope_parts_1_ground	1 Ground, Substructure (Groundwork; floor beds; retaining walls; foundations)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_2_structure	2 Structure primary elements, carcass (Structural building frame; external and internal walls; floors; stairs; roofs)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_3_secondary	3 Secondary elements, openings (Openings in walls, floors and roofs; windows; doors)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_4_finishes	4 Finishes (External and internal wall finishes; floor, ceiling and roof finishes)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_5_mechanical	5 Services, mainly mechanical (Heating, cooling, water systems (HVAC); sanitary)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_6_electrical	6 Services, mainly electrical (Electrical supply; lighting; communication; transport; security)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_6+_renewables	6+ Renewable Energy Systems (‘Yes’ if assessment includes PV, heat pump, or other RE systems)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_7_facilities	7 Facilities (‘Fixed’ facilities: Sanitary; food processing facilities, etc.)	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_parts_8_fittings	8 Fittings (‘Mobile’ fittings: user (furniture); food processing; storage; etc.)	Categorical (Predefined)

273

274 The scope summary attribute for building parts included in assessment scope (scope_parts) is
 275 an aggregated indicator obtained by transformation of the yes/no value for the respective
 276 scope_parts_* attributes into a concatenated six-character string using the first letter of each
 277 building part class. Sample values for the six-character summary string are:

- 278
- GLEISA = All standard elements considered = full scope
 - 279 • GLE-- = Structure, Foundation and Envelope, no internal elements or technical services
 - 280 • --E-S = Envelope and building services only.

281 **Life cycle stages:** The datasets include specific attributes to describe the scope regarding life
 282 cycle stages and life cycle modules covered in the respective case studies. The coding logic
 283 follows the respective European standard for building LCA EN 15978.

284 *Table 7: CORE attributes for 'assessment methods'; 'life cycle stages'*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
scope_LCS_A123	A1-3 Production	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_A4	A4 Transport	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_A5	A5 Construction	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B1	B1 Use	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B2	B2 Maintenance	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B3	B3 Repair	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B4	B4 Replacement	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B5	B5 Refurbishment	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6	B6 Operational energy use	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B7	B7 Operational water use	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B8	B8 Mobility	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_C1	C1 De-construction	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_C2	C2 Transport	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_C3	C3 Waste processing	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_C4	C4 Disposal	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_D	(D) Reuse, recovery, recycling	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_handling_D	Handling of module D?	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_heating	Scope of operational energy values, i.e., including either of: Heating, Ventilation, Cooling, Domestic Hot Water, Lighting, Appliances	Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_ventilation		Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_cooling		Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_DHW		Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_lighting		Categorical (Predefined)
scope_LCS_B6_appliances		Categorical (Predefined)

285
 286 Similarly, the scope for life cycle stages included in the assessment scope (scope_LCS) and
 287 scope summary for life cycle modules (scope_LCM) represent aggregated indicators of the
 288 respective life cycle scope attributes (scope_LCS_*), expressed per stages or modules,
 289 respectively. Sample values for scoping summary for life cycle stages and life cycle modules are:

- 290 • Life cycle stages
 - 291 ○ ABC- = Whole life cycle assessment (A-C), not considering mod D.
 - 292 ○ A--- = Cradle to gate/site assessment (A), not covering use, EoL, no mod D.
 - 293 ○ A-C- = Cradle to grave (A+C), but not covering use phase, no module D.
- 294 • Life cycle modules
 - 295 ○ PCMRODW = All life cycle modules covered
 - 296 ○ P-M--D- = Production; Maintenance, repair, replacement; and Deconstruction,
 297 transport.

298 Life cycle inventory

299 *Table 8: CORE attributes for 'life cycle inventory'*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
inv_energy_consumption	Operational energy consumption value [per m ² GFA/year]	Numerical [kWh/m ² /a]

inv_energy_consumption_description	Description of operational energy consumption values used for assessing the use phase (B6). E.g., Building performance simulation; benchmark estimation, statistic data; meter data	String (Free text)
inv_energy_consumption_type	Type of building energy source, performance simulation or real-world measurement as documented in the paper, otherwise considered based on estimation or benchmarks.	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_mass_total	Total mass of the building (all materials)	Numerical [kg]
inv_mat_mass_total_m2	Total mass of the building per m ² (all materials)	Numerical [kg/m ²]
inv_mat_1_type	1st: Material [dropdown]	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_1_mass	1st: Quantity [kg]	Numerical [kg]
inv_mat_2_type	2nd: Material [dropdown]	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_2_mass	2nd: Quantity [kg]	Numerical [kg]
inv_mat_3_type	3rd: Material [dropdown]	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_3_mass	3rd: Quantity [kg]	Numerical [kg]
inv_mat_4_type	4th: Material [dropdown]	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_4_mass	4th: Quantity [kg]	Numerical [kg]
inv_mat_5_type	5th: Material [dropdown]	Categorical (Predefined)
inv_mat_5_mass	5th: Quantity [kg]	Numerical [kg]

300 Note that regarding the life cycle inventory (LCI) we here focus on the primary data of resource
301 and energy use, i.e. foreground LCI. Secondary attributes include: inv_mat_mass_total_capita
302 (Total mass of the building per capita (all materials)); inv_mat_mass_sum_top_5 (Sum mass of
303 top 5 materials reported); inv_mat_mass_ratio (Ratio of total mass to top 5 sum). Furthermore,
304 the mass of individual materials (as reported via the top 5 materials) and their respective
305 material intensity (MI) were computed and are indicated by a prefix to the attribute code:

- 306 • mass_* (Computed mass of individual top 5 materials and respective mapping to
307 Eurostat material classes (See classification of building materials));
- 308 • mi_* (Computed material intensity (MI) of individual top 5 materials and respective
309 mapping to material categories of Fishman et al.¹¹ as well as Eurostat material classes
310 (See classification of building materials))

311 Detailed information on the list of materials and their respective mapping to Eurostat classes is
312 presented in data processing, classification of building materials chapter.

313 *Table 9: CORE attributes for 'life cycle inventory'; computed material intensity attributes as in Fishman et al. ¹¹*

Code	Description	Type [unit]
xmi_aluminum	Computed material intensity for aluminium	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_copper	Computed material intensity for copper	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_brick	Computed material intensity for brick	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_concrete	Computed material intensity for concrete materials	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_glass	Computed material intensity for glass	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_plastics	Computed material intensity for plastics	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_steel	Computed material intensity for steel	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_wood	Computed material intensity for wood construction products	Numerical [kg/m ²]
xmi_other	Computed material intensity for other construction materials	Numerical [kg/m ²]

314 Indicator results

315 *Table 10: CORE attributes for 'indicator results'*

Code	Description	Data type / unit remarks
GHG_sum_em_m2a	Sum Embodied GHG emissions per m ² per year	Numerical [kgCO ₂ e/m ² /a]

GHG_EC_share	Embodied GHG emissions share on total (% contrib)	Numerical [decimal]
GHG_OC_share	Operational GHG emissions share on total (% contrib)	Numerical [decimal]
GHG_A123_m2a	A1-A3 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_A45_m2a	A4-A5 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_B1234_m2a	B1-B4 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_B5_m2a	B5 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_B67_m2a	B6-B7 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_C12_m2a	C1-C2 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_C34_m2a	C3-C4 GHG emissions (original, as per source)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_A123_m2a_harm	A1-A3 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_A45_m2a_harm	A4-A5 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_B1234_m2a_harm	B1-B4 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_B67_m2a_harm	B6-B7 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_C12_m2a_harm	C1-C2 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_C34_m2a_harm	C3-C4 GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_sum_em_m2a_harm	Sum Embodied GHG emissions (EU-ECB, harmonized acc. Röck et al. 2022)	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_sum_em_capita_a	Sum Embodied GHG emissions per capita	Numerical [kgCO2e/cap/a]
GHG_A_capita_a	LCS A1-5 Embodied GHG emissions per capita	Numerical [kgCO2e/cap/a]
GHG_B_em_capita_a	LCS B1-4 Embodied GHG emissions per capita	Numerical [kgCO2e/cap/a]
GHG_B_op_capita_a	LCS B6-7 Operational GHG emissions per capita	Numerical [kgCO2e/cap/a]
GHG_C_capita_a	LCS C1-4 Embodied GHG emissions per capita	Numerical [kgCO2e/cap/a]
GHG_P1_sum_m2a	Sum GHG Ground (1) [kgCO2e/m2/a]	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_P2_sum_m2a	Sum GHG Structure (2) [kgCO2e/m2/a]	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_P34_sum_m2a	Sum Envelope (3, 4) [kgCO2e/m2/a]	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]
GHG_P4_sum_m2a	Sum GHG Internal (4) [kgCO2e/m2/a]	Numerical [kgCO2e/m2/a]

316 **Missing information**

317 Where specified in the attribute description document, sample values specified using closed
318 brackets ([...]) indicate a closed list of values, i.e., all possible values are shown or indicated,
319 while open brackets (][...]) indicate an open list, i.e., more than the value shown are possible
320 (and contained in the dataset). The following syntax was applied to indicate missing
321 information for numerical and categorical attributes respectively:

- 322 • ‘n/a’ indicates missing information for numerical attributes. The ‘n/a’ abbreviation is
323 automatically recognized by data processing packages such as Python Pandas and will
324 show as an empty value once loaded.
- 325 • ‘No data’ is used to indicate missing data for categorical attributes. It that an attribute
326 has been reviewed but no data was identified in the underlying study.

327 **Technical Validation**

328 **Data overview**

329 The dataset includes buildings from various parts of the World, with most cases in Europe.
330 Figure 2 illustrates geographic coverage of the dataset on a global map, highlighting the origin
331 of cases as well as persisting gaps of building data concerning resource use, energy

332 performance and whole life cycle GHG emissions. Composition of the dataset with regards to
333 distribution of key attributes is presented in Figure 3. The dataset covers both residential and
334 non-residential buildings and distinguishes various building use subtypes. Around 2/3 of the
335 dataset are residential buildings, with 40% of cases representing single family houses (SFH) and
336 around 25% multi-family houses (MFH). Close to 3/4 of the dataset are describing massive
337 types of construction, such as massive brick (40%), massive wood (17%), or massive concrete
338 (13%). Most cases are buildings completed within the last 10 years, with 49% of cases
339 constructed 2015-2019 and 14% after 2020 (>2022). Another big fraction are buildings without
340 information on the construction year (22%). Distribution of the building size in terms of floor
341 area shows that the majority, more than 2/3 of cases are within the interval of 0-5000 m².

342 **Data consistency**

343 **Carbon emission data**

344 *Figure 4* presents the distribution of harmonised values for embodied carbon intensity per m²
345 and year by individual life cycle stages. The highest carbon intensity is observed for the
346 production stage (A123) with a median value around 6.5 kgCO_{2e}/m²a, and extreme values just
347 above 30 kgCO_{2e}/m²a. Followed by use-phase related embodied carbon (B1234) and emissions
348 related to end-of-life (C34). Production stage emission values are the most emission values in
349 this dataset as they are directly related to quantity of construction materials and do not
350 depend on additional life cycle scenarios (as is the case for assessment of emissions for all
351 other life cycle stages). All values are affected by the methodological choices in the respective
352 studies. For example, for some case in Figure 3 negative emission values can be observed for
353 production stage (A123), deconstruction process stage (C12), or end-of-life (C34). These are
354 due to methodological decisions made in the respective original sources, such as the
355 consideration of biogenic carbon uptake as negative values during the production stage, or
356 benefits of avoided emissions through recycling or energy recovery at end of life.

357 Further information can be obtained via the respective attributes on 'assessment method' or
358 'life cycle inventory, for example to relate emission values to material intensity.

359 Analyses of embodied and operational carbon intensity for different types of building uses and
360 energy performance levels are presented in existing journal articles^{1,19}. The European subset
361 was subject to an in-depth analysis of the carbon intensity of different life cycle stages,
362 distinguished for different building use (sub)types¹⁸.

363 *Figure 5* presents details on the embodied carbon intensity for selected building uses and types
364 of structure. It shows subplots for the contribution of different life cycle stages as well as the
365 contribution from different building parts. The plots illustrate how these contributions can vary
366 or different building types and how the dataset can be used to obtain contribution analyses for
367 different subsets to inform benchmarking and bottom-up target development.

368 **Energy performance data**

369 Energy performance data have been retrieved for both the energy intensity in terms of final
370 energy demand as well as the resulting cumulative energy demand (CED) for both operational
371 and material-related embodied energy. The resulting energy performance data shows values
372 for operational energy demand of around 70 kWh/m²a (median value) and ranges up to 350
373 kWh/m²a (upper IQR), with extreme values reaching close to 700 kWh/m²a. The database
374 includes information on building's energy performance class (bldg_energy_performance) as
375 well as the GHG emissions from building operation (GHG_B67).

376 **Material intensity data**

377 The dataset contains material information for the total mass of the building
378 (inv_mat_mass_total) as well as on the type and quantity of the top five building materials in

379 terms of mass contribution. Information on the top five materials has been processed and
380 transformed to offer individual attributes on material mass and material intensity for each of
381 those materials, as well as to map those material with Eurostat primary raw material categories
382 and compute the respective material intensity per m². *Figure 6* presents the distribution of
383 material intensity per m² by Eurostat material category for the full dataset. It shows that the
384 highest material intensity is observed for concrete, cement and aggregate (CCA) materials with
385 a median value of around 1000 kg/m² and ranging up to around 2000 kg/m². Second largest
386 intensity, on average, is observed for non-CCA minerals, with a median value of only around
387 100 kg/m² albeit ranging up to 1200 kg/m² (upper IQR) or even beyond 2000 kg/m², in extreme
388 cases. *Figure 7* further details on the distribution of material intensity values for selected
389 building materials (concrete, steel, wood, brick), showing trends for different types of building
390 structure. It illustrates how, similar to the embodied carbon contribution analyses presented in
391 *Figure 5*, the dataset can inform the identification of material use patterns and definition of
392 indicative benchmarks for material intensity.

393 **Data validation**

394 To validate the data, we are contextualizing the values with numbers of national input-output
395 (I/O) accounting by the example of data for France. Given the large amount of data collected
396 for this country, we can compare our values with the national emissions reports. We use the
397 example of France, which has the most entries in the dataset, and compare with a recent I/O
398 analysis carried out to quantify the embodied life-cycle GHG emissions of the French building
399 stock⁴⁰. As discussed in previous publications⁴¹, large differences are observed between I/O and
400 process-based LCAs, so a direct comparison of the absolute GHG emissions would not be
401 relevant for validation. However, the contribution of the individual life cycle stages can be used
402 to assess consistency of the models and datasets.

403 *Figure 8* shows the I/O results regarding the relative contribution of embodied emissions from
404 buildings in France, broken down by “industrial production” (includes A1-A3 and B1-5),
405 “construction & transport” (A4-5, C1-2) and “waste processing” (C3-C4). Other sectors, such as
406 “services”, which are assessed from an input-output perspective, but not at the process-based
407 level, were not included in this visualisation. This sectoral aggregation was necessary to enable
408 a comparison with I/O-based results, which are usually more aggregated than process-based
409 ones. It is part of the novelty of this database to enable a more explicit differentiation between
410 building types and also between different stages of the building life cycle. Such differentiation
411 is required for various downstream uses, such as for using building data to model the various
412 building stock activities (new construction, replacement, refurbishment) from the perspective
413 of national accounts. For the process-based values of this dataset, the life cycle stages were
414 multiplied by the annual activities of the French building stock (with 2019 as the reference year.
415 As the B1-4 modules are not included in the statistics, the emission factors were multiplied by
416 the number of renovated buildings as an indication, following the method presented by Truger
417 et al.⁴².

418 As presented in *Figure 8*, we find that the relative shares of “materials production” as well as
419 “construction & transport” are quite similar, with less than 4% difference. The main difference
420 is “waste processing”, which accounts for 5.9% of emissions in the input-output analysis, but
421 less than 1% in this study. This is not likely due to a data gap in the database, as this life cycle
422 stage was filled in for all entries used in this analysis. This could be due to the overlap between
423 the life cycle stages; Waste processing also takes place in A5, B1-4 as well as C1, and is
424 considered in these modules, but not in C3-C4. It could also be due to the difference between
425 I/O and process-based databases. Steubing et al.⁴¹ estimated that waste management activities
426 are on average 90% lower when assessed with process-based results, which also seems to be
427 the case in this comparison. Overall, apart from the deviation at the waste processing stage,
428 the results appear to be consistent with existing I/O-based national assessments in their

429 relative proportions. The data presented with this article can further be utilized to provide
430 complementary insights into the distribution between life cycle stages or different building
431 parts, as shown for example in Figure 5.

432 **Usage Notes**

433 ***General remarks***

434 In the compilation and interpretation of the data presented here, a distinction is made
435 between three key aspects: Firstly, (1) it should be shown that and how large amounts of data
436 can be analyzed in a targeted manner and which questions arise in the process. There were
437 gaps, particularly in the level of detail and completeness of the description of case studies,
438 which hinder their systematic evaluation and classification into a typology. To overcome these
439 problems, extended lists of attributes for the description of case studies are presented and
440 recommended for future use; (2) The indicators presented in the article are intended to
441 improve the general understanding of orders of magnitude and size ratios as well as
442 bandwidths in politics and industry. This particularly applies to indicators for upfront embodied
443 impacts (A1-A5) as sub-values of the WLC results. There is still little experience on those
444 numbers available in both research and building practice, and the bandwidths shown indicate
445 potential for optimization in design and material selection. Furthermore, the current
446 proportions of values upfront impacts (A1-A5) on the one hand and in-use embodied impact
447 values (B2-B4) on the other are indicated and reasons for a possible neglect of values for end-
448 of-life (C1-C2) are given. While useful for benchmarking and contextualization, the average
449 values and bandwidths presented are not intended for use in the balancing of individual
450 buildings and do not replace a detailed calculation along a consistent a comprehensive
451 assessment method; (3) The GBDB database with detailed attributes describing the underlying
452 building cases supports the search for case studies that are as close as possible to one's own
453 object of assessment. The data can thus be used for comparison and contextualization of
454 building LCA studies in both research and industry practice. Remaining uncertainties due to
455 missing or imprecise information on assumptions and boundary conditions must be considered
456 on a case-by-case basis.

457 ***Exemplary use cases***

458 The following use cases for the data and descriptor presented here are particularly highlighted
459 by the authors. The data and this descriptor can be used, for example, to inform and support
460 users seeking to:

- 461 a) Obtain and presenting orders of magnitude for whole life cycle GHG emissions, or
462 whole life carbon, in an area that has not yet been studied so frequently and where
463 many stakeholders in politics and practice lack a sense of scale
- 464 b) Understand bandwidths that indicate optimization potentials from an embodied and
465 whole life cycle GHG emissions perspective
- 466 c) Obtain and present size ratios, e.g. A1-A3 to B2-B4, including answering questions such
467 as how A4-A5 and C1-C2 can be neglected
- 468 d) Find specific cases in the database as close as possible to your own example/needs
- 469 e) Gather experience on the type, scope and quality of information on case studies,
470 including information on gaps (see "missing data") and stimulating more
471 comprehensive documentation in future to improve transparency and traceability
- 472 f) Gather methodological insights in the evaluation of large amounts of data from various
473 sources
- 474 g) Derive guidance on information requirements – data attributes and reporting formats –
475 for the documentation of case studies in their own context

476

477 **Carbon benchmarking**

478 In the following we outline how the carbon emissions data can be used for benchmarking in
479 practice. Depending on the specific use case, benchmarks can be defined at different levels and
480 then used to obtain a first estimate of whole life cycle GHG emissions for new building projects
481 in different regional contexts, for different building types, structural systems or energy
482 performance classes. In principle, all attributes available in this database can be used for
483 defining an appropriate subset for benchmarking.

484 **Multi-level benchmark definition:** Benchmark definition is possible at different levels, meaning
485 the consideration of fewer or more attributes to define the subset a benchmark is based on.
486 Table 11 presents examples of level-2, level-3, and level-4 benchmarks. Level-2 benchmark
487 example herein uses the site region and building use subtype; Level-3 adds the layer of energy
488 performance class or building structure type; and the level-4 example combined all of the
489 previously mentioned to an already fairly specific benchmarking subset considering site region,
490 building use subtype, energy performance class, and building structure type. It is important to
491 note that lower-level benchmarking utilizes more data points and is thus more robust but also
492 more general with potentially large variability, while higher level benchmarking is more specific
493 but based on fewer data thus potentially more biased.

494 **Application considering ambition level:** Users can adjust the assumptions to fit the ambition
495 level for the respective project. For example, users can decide if their project aims for a whole
496 life carbon performance with low, medium, or high ambition and then apply the related
497 benchmark values for 25th, 50th, or 75th percentile, respectively. This decision can be made for
498 each of the life cycle stages to allow for a focus of efforts, for example to reduce emissions in
499 those life cycle stages that represent carbon hotspots.

500 The examples presented in Table 11 show how the benchmarks change when using different
501 benchmarking levels and varying the attribute selection. Various relevant insights can be
502 derived from the different cases presented here. For example, Level-2 benchmarks can be
503 defined for different world regions (Western Europe, Eastern Asia), as well as for different
504 building use subtypes (SFH, MFH). One can observe the difference in both embodied life cycle
505 emissions, as well as operational emissions from benchmarking these different typologies.
506 While, for example, the GHG emissions from the production stage (A1-A3) already differ
507 substantially between the two settings, it is especially the difference in operational emissions
508 (B6-B7) that stands out. Together, these differences lead to a substantially different profile of
509 carbon hotspots across the whole life cycle, with 2/3 whole life cycle emissions being
510 'embodied' in the Western Europe case, while the Eastern Asia case this is reversed and around
511 74% of emissions are likely linked to building operation. Similarly, level-3 benchmarks can be
512 defined within the Western European, SFH setting to indicate values for different types of
513 energy performance (2.a) or type of building structure (2.b). Here it becomes evident that for
514 New Advanced energy performance (2.a) the emissions from building operation are
515 substantially lowered while at the same time the indicate emission from the production stage
516 increase above the related level-2 benchmarks (1.a). Overall, this leads to a shift in carbon
517 hotspots, where less than 10% are related to building operation and 90% being embodied
518 emissions. Almost 50% of whole life cycle emissions are here linked to the production stage,
519 arising upfront ahead of building use. The case of building structures with frame wood (2.b)
520 shows that, while the overall distribution of the carbon hotspots may not change that much,
521 there is potential in reducing the absolute embodied and particularly the upfront GHG
522 emissions when option for low carbon material solutions. These two cases, as well as the level-
523 4 benchmark (3) also show a potentially unintended effect of this current approach, related to
524 operational GHG emissions. Comparing the operational emissions across the three cases (2.a,
525 2.b, 3), one can observe that they are fairly low for the new advanced benchmarking (2.a),
526 which is expected as here energy performance class is among the attributes defining the
527 benchmarking subset. At the same time, for the frame wood case (2.b) we find potentially very

528 high operational emissions (see 75th percentile), which is due to the energy performance of the
 529 underlying cases in the data set, some of which seem to have above average operational
 530 emissions. The level-4 benchmarking example (3) overall indicates similar values than the first,
 531 more general level 2 benchmarking (1.a). However, the considerably lower number of cases
 532 (count) that this last example is based on makes clear, that in other cases there could also be a
 533 strong bias in level-4 benchmarks. At time, level-4 benchmarking or beyond may not be feasible
 534 due to the prevailing limitations concerning diversity, completeness and overall number of
 535 cases in the database. Table 11 further shows how the general benchmark values, computed
 536 per m² and year (kgCO₂e/m²a for an RSP of 50 years, are then applied for an example building
 537 case (floor area 140,00 m²) to obtain indicative building level emissions.

538 *Table 11: Examples for the multi-level benchmark definition and building application of whole life cycle GHG*
 539 *emissions for different regions, building types, types of structure, and energy performance classes, respectively.*

1.a) Level-2 benchmark example: Western Europe, SFH.									
Life cycle stages	GHG emissions (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)				Building Floor Area (m ²)	GHG Emissions (kgCO ₂ e)			Hotspots % Median
	Count	25th	50th Median	75th		25th	50th Median	75th	
Production [A1-A3]	24	273,50	311,50	332,00	140,00	38.290	43.610	46.480	40%
Construction [A4-A5]	23	19,00	37,50	39,50		2.660	5.250	5.530	5%
Use, embodied [B1-B4]	23	150,50	197,50	220,00		21.070	27.650	30.800	26%
Use, operation [B6-B7]	191	68,50	214,50	520,00		9.590	30.030	72.800	28%
End of life [C1-C4]	24	10,20	10,23	12,24		1.428	1.432	1.714	1%
WLC GHG emissions	-	1.374	2.316	3.267		73.038	107.972	157.324	100%
1.b) Level-2 benchmark example: Eastern Asia, MFH.									
Life cycle stages	GHG emissions (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)				Building Floor Area (m ²)	GHG Emissions (kgCO ₂ e)			Hotspots % Median
	Count	25th	50th Median	75th		25th	50th Median	75th	
Production [A1-A3]	45	309,00	412,50	426,50	140,00	43.260	57.750	59.710	18%
Construction [A4-A5]	36	29,50	45,50	66,50		4.130	6.370	9.310	2%
Use, embodied [B1-B4]	21	33,50	84,00	85,50		4.690	11.760	11.970	4%
Use, operation [B6-B7]	43	967,50	1.720,50	2.617,00		135.450	240.870	366.380	74%
End of life [C1-C4]	33	35,69	53,88	71,98		4.997	7.543	10.077	2%
WLC GHG emissions	-	1.374	2.316	3.267		192.527	324.293	457.447	100%
2.a) Level-3 benchmark example: Western Europe, SFH, New Advanced.									
Life cycle stages	GHG emissions (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)				Building Floor Area (m ²)	GHG Emissions (kgCO ₂ e)			Hotspots % Median
	Count	25th	50th Median	75th		25th	50th Median	75th	
Production [A1-A3]	6	316,00	319,50	329,00	140,00	44.240	44.730	46.060	49%
Construction [A4-A5]	6	39,50	40,00	41,00		5.530	5.600	5.740	6%
Use, embodied [B1-B4]	6	226,50	227,00	227,50		31.710	31.780	31.850	34%
Use, operation [B6-B7]	61	53,00	59,50	62,50		7.420	8.330	8.750	9%
End of life [C1-C4]	6	12,72	12,73	12,73		1.781	1.782	1.782	2%
WLC GHG emissions	-	1.374	2.316	3.267		90.681	92.222	94.182	100%
2.b) Level-3 benchmark example: Western Europe, SFH, Frame Wood.									
Life cycle stages	GHG emissions (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)				Building Floor Area (m ²)	GHG Emissions (kgCO ₂ e)			Hotspots % Median
	Count	25th	50th Median	75th		25th	50th Median	75th	
Production [A1-A3]	6	201,50	205,00	213,50	140,00	28.210	28.700	29.890	45%
Construction [A4-A5]	6	19,00	19,50	20,00		2.660	2.730	2.800	4%
Use, embodied [B1-B4]	6	155,00	156,00	159,50		21.700	21.840	22.330	34%
Use, operation [B6-B7]	23	57,00	69,00	952,50		7.980	9.660	133.350	15%
End of life [C1-C4]	6	10,14	10,14	10,65		1.420	1.420	1.491	2%
WLC GHG emissions	-	1.374	2.316	3.267		61.970	64.350	189.861	100%
3) Level-4 benchmark example: Western Europe, SFH, New Standard, Massive Brick.									
Life cycle stages	GHG emissions (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)				Building	GHG Emissions (kgCO ₂ e)			Hotspots
	Count	25th	50th Median	75th	Floor Area (m ²)	25th	50th Median	75th	% Median

	Count	25th	50th Median	75th	Floor Area (m ²)	25th	50th Median	75th	% Median
Production [A1-A3]	6	297,00	300,50	310,00	140,00	41.580	42.070	43.400	33%
Construction [A4-A5]	6	39,00	39,00	40,00		5.460	5.460	5.600	4%
Use, embodied [B1-B4]	6	214,50	215,50	217,00		30.030	30.170	30.380	23%
Use, operation [B6-B7]	108	108,00	355,00	545,50		15.120	49.700	76.370	39%
End of life [C1-C4]	6	9,22	9,73	10,24		1.291	1.362	1.434	1%
WLC GHG emissions	-	1.374	2.316	3.267		93.481	128.762	157.184	100%

540 **Contributions and versioning**

541 **Future development**

542 The GBDB ambition is to continuously expand the amount and quality of openly accessible data
543 on building's resource use, energy performance, and whole life cycle impacts. We see this WLC
544 database as the first version of what we aim to update and extend towards both increased
545 global coverage and elaborated attribute information in future iterations. While the
546 CarbEnMats seed focuses on WLC emissions, future data contributions can extend both the
547 level of detail as well as the scope of indicators captured to include a more comprehensive
548 environmental footprint (via complete sets of LCA indicators). Future data contributions are
549 expected to arise from currently ongoing research on modelling the European building stock via
550 a comprehensive archetype-based approach for each of the 27 Member States. Furthermore,
551 global collaboration around the development of common exchange formats for detailed
552 reporting of resource use and WLC emissions, such as the efforts led by the Global Building
553 Data Initiative (www.gbdi.io) are expected to yield substantial data contributions in the future.

554 **Contributions**

555 The authors encourage contributions to GBDB from other researchers and practitioners. A global
556 network of experts on the topic of WLC reporting and data exchange via the Global Building
557 Data Initiative (www.gbdi.io). Interested parties are encouraged to get in touch and contribute
558 their data via the related public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/mroeck/carbenmats-buildings>). Contributors will be prominently cited and invited for co-authorship in future
559 publications. This article shall serve as a joint reference for future activities and publications. If
560 you'd like to contribute or leave feedback, please get in touch with the corresponding author
561 and/or open an issue on GitHub.

563 **Versioning**

564 GBDB uses semantic versioning logic⁴³, based on the MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH numbering pattern.
565 Patch version increments for smaller, backward compatible bug fixes. Patches indicate that the
566 database has been fixed or improved in a way that should break existing integrations. Minor
567 version increments when adding functionality in a way that is also backward compatible. Minor
568 changes might involve adjustments to existing logic or attributes and should never be updated
569 in downstream uses without testing how it affects the specific downstream application. The
570 patch number is always reset to 0 after a minor version increment. Major version increment
571 when introducing breaking changes that are not backward compatible. Such may be substantial
572 changes to the GBDB data structure. A major version change indicates that users will likely
573 need to change how their software integrates with the database. As with patch version
574 increments, all minor versions are reset to 0 after a major version step. Additional labels can be
575 used as an extension to the MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH format, for example to indicate pre-releases
576 or other metadata aspects such as the nick name of a specific version. The latest version of this
577 database will always be available via the public GitHub repository. The version used for this
578 descriptor is '0.2.0-carbenmats'.

579 **Concluding remarks**

580 The approach to define reference values and targets for specific building designs during spatial
581 planning and building design processes, as well as for contextualization and checking the
582 plausibility of results obtained in building specific assessment or other studies.

583 In conclusion, the authors hope that the present database and similar efforts for advancing
584 quality and availability of open building data will further improve the data situation and enable
585 more specific benchmarking, target setting as well concrete action reducing resource use,
586 energy performance, as well as whole life cycle GHG emissions of buildings in the future.

587 **Code Availability**

588 Data and code related to this descriptor are available via the GBDB public GitHub repository
589 (<https://github.com/mroeck/carbenmats-buildings>) and the related release via Zenodo
590 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13221978>). The data collection template (DCT) and additional
591 files for data processing are available via the Embodied Carbon of European Buildings Database
592 (<https://github.com/mroeck/Embodied-Carbon-of-European-Buildings-Database>). The dataset
593 files, template as well as all scripts are published under a GNU General Public License v3.0. The
594 GNU General Public License is a free, copyleft license for software and other kinds of works. We
595 encourage to review, reuse, and refine the data and scripts and eventually share-alike.

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626 **Competing interests**

627 All authors declare that they have no known conflicts of interest.

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729 **Figures**

730
731 *Figure 1: Conceptual overview of attribute types and examples.*

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734 *Figure 2: Global map indicating country and count of building cases. The map indicates for which countries building*
735 *cases are included in the dataset. The color gradient indicates the number of cases per country.*

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Distribution of values for selected key attributes

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Figure 3: Distribution of values for selected key attributes. Showing distribution of values for site region geoscheme, site country code, building year, building use subtype, building area interval, building floors above ground, building structure type, building energy class general, and scope life cycle stages, where (*) indicates inclusion of module D.

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Figure 4: Embodied carbon emission intensity - GHG emissions per m^2_{GFA}/a by life cycle stages (harmonised values, RSP=50 years).

Embodied carbon intensity for selected building uses and types of structure

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Figure 5: Embodied carbon intensity for selected building uses and types of structure. Showing subplots for (a) the contribution of different life cycle stages; and (b) the contribution from different building parts

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749 *Figure 6: Material intensity (mass per m²) by material categories of Heeren and Fishman. For improved overall*
 750 *readability, three outliers above 2000 kg/m² are omitted in this plot.*

751

752 *Figure 7: Distribution of material intensity values for selected building materials, using the mapping of MI classes*
 753 *according to Fishman et al 2024. To improve clarity of the plots custom axis limits are set [Concrete (0, 2000); Steel*
 754 *(0, 200); Wood (0, 500); Brick (0, 500)], omitting some extreme cases (Concrete: 3; Steel: 4; Wood: 3; Brick: 0).*

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Figure 8: Relative contribution to embodied emissions of buildings, from an input-output (bottom) and a process-based perspective (top) perspective, showing only data for France from the respective sources.

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